

1 Companion document

This document was created in order to provide extra explanation and formulation that was needed by the original model. In section 1, we provide the stationary conditions of the lower-level optimization, and in section 2, the complementary slackness conditions are provided. Section 3 explains the strong duality relation between primal and dual optimization problems of the lower level. Continuing with section 1.4, it provides the necessary linearization for the final mixed integer linear programming. Finally, section 1.5 represents input data necessary for the simulation.

1.1 Stationary Conditions

Stationary condition of the lower-level problem is as follows:

$$-\alpha_b \gamma_{b,1}^{\text{dyn}} + \gamma_b^{\text{ref},1} + \bar{\mu}_{b,1}^{\text{comf}} - \underline{\mu}_{b,1}^{\text{comf}} + \bar{\mu}_{b,1}^{\text{Tin}} - \underline{\mu}_{b,1}^{\text{Tin}} = 0, \quad \forall b. \quad (1a)$$

$$\gamma_{b,t-1}^{\text{dyn}} - \alpha_b \gamma_{b,t}^{\text{dyn}} + \bar{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{comf}} - \underline{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{comf}} + \bar{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{Tin}} - \underline{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{Tin}} = 0, \quad \forall b, t \in \{2, \dots, T-1\}. \quad (1b)$$

$$\gamma_{b,T-1}^{\text{dyn}} + \gamma_b^{\text{ref},T} + \bar{\mu}_{b,T}^{\text{comf}} - \underline{\mu}_{b,T}^{\text{comf}} + \bar{\mu}_{b,T}^{\text{Tin}} - \underline{\mu}_{b,T}^{\text{Tin}} = 0, \quad \forall b. \quad (1c)$$

$$u_b \sigma_t - \bar{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{comf}} - \underline{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{comf}} - \nu_{b,t}^\epsilon + \mu_{b,t}^\epsilon = 0, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (1d)$$

$$\lambda_t^{\text{Th}} + \gamma_{b,t}^{\text{Th}} = 0, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (1e)$$

$$\lambda_t^{\text{Retail}} + \gamma_{b,t}^{\text{El}} + \mu_{b,t}^{\text{Peak}} + \bar{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{Line}} - \nu_{b,t}^{\text{El}} = 0, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (1f)$$

$$-\lambda_t^{\text{FiT}} - \gamma_{b,t}^{\text{PV}} + \underline{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{Line}} - \nu_{b,t}^{\text{PV,FiT}} = 0, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (1g)$$

$$\gamma_{b,t}^{\text{El}} - \gamma_{b,t}^{\text{PV}} - \nu_{b,t}^{\text{PV,Th}} = 0, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (1h)$$

$$-\gamma_{b,t}^{\text{Th}} + \gamma_{b,t}^{\text{QHP}} - (1 - \alpha_b) R_b \gamma_{b,t}^{\text{dyn}} - \nu_{b,t}^{\text{HHP}} = 0, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (1i)$$

$$-\gamma_{b,T}^{\text{Th}} + \gamma_{b,T}^{\text{QHP}} - \nu_{b,T}^{\text{HHP}} = 0, \quad \forall b. \quad (1j)$$

$$\gamma_{b,t}^{\text{Th}} - \gamma_{b,t}^{\text{El}} + \gamma_{b,t}^{\text{PHP}} - \nu_{b,t}^{\text{HP}} = 0, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (1k)$$

$$-\gamma_{b,t}^{\text{QHP}} \text{COP}_k^{\text{WSHP}} - \gamma_{b,t}^{\text{PHP}} + \mu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{HP}} - \nu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{HP}} = 0, \quad \forall b, k, t. \quad (1l)$$

$$\gamma_{b,t}^{\text{Th}} + \gamma_{b,t}^{\text{Ch}} + (1 - \alpha_b) R_b \gamma_{b,t}^{\text{dyn}} - \nu_{b,t}^{\text{HCh}} = 0, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (1m)$$

$$\gamma_{b,T}^{\text{Th}} + \gamma_{b,T}^{\text{Ch}} - \nu_{b,T}^{\text{HCh}} = 0, \quad \forall b. \quad (1n)$$

$$\gamma_{b,t}^{\text{Th}} - \gamma_{b,t}^{\text{El}} + \gamma_{b,t}^{\text{PCh}} - \nu_{b,t}^{\text{Ch}} = 0, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (1o)$$

$$-\gamma_{b,t}^{\text{Ch}} \text{COP}_k^{\text{C}} - \gamma_{b,t}^{\text{PCh}} + \mu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{Ch}} - \nu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{Ch}} = 0, \quad \forall b, k, t. \quad (1p)$$

$$\lambda^{\text{CfP}} - \sum_{t=1}^T \mu_{b,t}^{\text{Peak}} - \nu_b^{\text{peak}} = 0, \quad \forall b. \quad (1q)$$

1.2 Complementary slackness conditions

The complementary slackness conditions of the lower level is as follows:

$$0 \leq \bar{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{comf}} \perp (T_{b,t}^{\text{des}} + \bar{T}^{\text{comf}} + \epsilon_{b,t} - T_{b,t}^{\text{in}}) \geq 0, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (2a)$$

$$0 \leq \underline{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{comf}} \perp (T_{b,t}^{\text{in}} - T_{b,t}^{\text{des}} + \underline{T}^{\text{comf}} + \epsilon_{b,t}) \geq 0, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (2b)$$

$$0 \leq \mu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{HP}} \perp (\theta_{k,t} \bar{P}_b^{\text{HP}} - P_{b,k,t}^{\theta,\text{HP}}) \geq 0, \quad \forall b, k, t. \quad (2c)$$

$$0 \leq \mu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{Ch}} \perp (\theta_{k,t} \bar{P}_b^{\text{C}} - P_{b,k,t}^{\theta,\text{C}}) \geq 0, \quad \forall b, k, t. \quad (2d)$$

$$0 \leq \mu_{b,t}^{\text{Peak}} \perp (P_b^{\text{peak}} - P_{b,t}^{\text{El}}) \geq 0, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (2e)$$

$$0 \leq \bar{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{Line}} \perp (\bar{P}_b^{\text{Line}} - P_{b,t}^{\text{El}}) \geq 0, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (2f)$$

$$0 \leq \underline{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{Line}} \perp (\bar{P}_b^{\text{Line}} - P_{b,t}^{\text{PV,FiT}}) \geq 0, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (2g)$$

$$0 \leq \bar{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{Tin}} \perp (\bar{T}_b^{\text{in}} - T_{b,t}^{\text{in}}) \geq 0, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (2h)$$

$$0 \leq \underline{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{Tin}} \perp (T_{b,t}^{\text{in}} - \underline{T}_b^{\text{in}}) \geq 0, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (2i)$$

$$0 \leq \mu_{b,t}^\epsilon \perp (\bar{\epsilon} - \epsilon_{b,t}) \geq 0, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (2j)$$

$$0 \leq \nu_{b,t}^\epsilon \perp \epsilon_{b,t} \geq 0, \quad (2k)$$

$$0 \leq \nu_{b,t}^{\text{El}} \perp P_{b,t}^{\text{El}} \geq 0, \quad (2l)$$

$$0 \leq \nu_{b,t}^{\text{PV,FiT}} \perp P_{b,t}^{\text{PV,FiT}} \geq 0, \quad (2m)$$

$$0 \leq \nu_{b,t}^{\text{PV,Th}} \perp P_{b,t}^{\text{PV,Th}} \geq 0, \forall b, t \quad (2n)$$

$$0 \leq \nu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{Hp}} \perp P_{b,k,t}^{\theta, \text{Hp}} \geq 0, \forall b, k, t \quad (2o)$$

$$0 \leq \nu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{Ch}} \perp P_{b,k,t}^{\theta, \text{C}} \geq 0, \forall b, k, t \quad (2p)$$

$$0 \leq \nu_{b,t}^{\text{Hp}} \perp P_{b,t}^{\text{Hp}} \geq 0, \forall b, t \quad (2q)$$

$$0 \leq \nu_{b,t}^{\text{Ch}} \perp P_{b,t}^{\text{Ch}} \geq 0, \forall b, t \quad (2r)$$

$$0 \leq \nu_{b,t}^{\text{HHp}} \perp H_{b,t}^{\text{Hp}} \geq 0, \forall b, t \quad (2s)$$

$$0 \leq \nu_{b,t}^{\text{HCh}} \perp H_{b,t}^{\text{Ch}} \geq 0, \forall b, t \quad (2t)$$

$$0 \leq \nu_b^{\text{peak}} \perp P_b^{\text{peak}} \geq 0, \forall b \quad (2u)$$

$$- \sum_{b=1}^B \sum_{t=1}^T \mu_{b,t}^{\text{Line}} \bar{P}_b^{\text{Line}}$$

$$- \sum_{b,t} \bar{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{Tin}} \bar{T}_b^{\text{in}} + \sum_{b,t} \underline{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{Tin}} \underline{T}_b^{\text{in}} - \sum_{b,t} \mu_{b,t}^\epsilon \bar{\epsilon}. \quad (3)$$

For the linearization of terms $\mu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{Hp}} \theta_{k,t} \bar{P}_b^{\text{Hp}}$ and $\mu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{Ch}} \theta_{k,t} \bar{P}_b^{\text{C}}$ the Big-M method used as follows:

$$w_{b,k,t}^{\text{Hp}} \geq 0, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{B}, k \in \mathcal{K}, t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (4)$$

$$w_{b,k,t}^{\text{Hp}} \leq M^{\text{Hp}} \theta_{k,t}, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{B}, k \in \mathcal{K}, t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (5)$$

$$w_{b,k,t}^{\text{Hp}} \leq \mu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{Hp}}, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{B}, k \in \mathcal{K}, t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (6)$$

$$w_{b,k,t}^{\text{Hp}} \geq \mu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{Hp}} - M^{\text{Hp}}(1 - \theta_{k,t}), \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{B}, k \in \mathcal{K}, t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (7)$$

$$w_{b,k,t}^{\text{Ch}} \geq 0, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{B}, k \in \mathcal{K}, t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (8)$$

$$w_{b,k,t}^{\text{Ch}} \leq M^{\text{Ch}} \theta_{k,t}, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{B}, k \in \mathcal{K}, t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (9)$$

$$w_{b,k,t}^{\text{Ch}} \leq \mu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{Ch}}, \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{B}, k \in \mathcal{K}, t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (10)$$

$$w_{b,k,t}^{\text{Ch}} \geq \mu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{Ch}} - M^{\text{Ch}}(1 - \theta_{k,t}), \quad \forall b \in \mathcal{B}, k \in \mathcal{K}, t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (11)$$

where M^{Hp} and M^{Ch} are valid upper bounds for $\mu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{Hp}}$ and $\mu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{Ch}}$, respectively, and $\theta_{k,t} \in \{0, 1\}$. Then the bilinear terms can be replaced by:

$$\mu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{Hp}} \theta_{k,t} \bar{P}_b^{\text{Hp}} = \bar{P}_b^{\text{Hp}} w_{b,k,t}^{\text{Hp}}, \quad (12)$$

$$\mu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{Ch}} \theta_{k,t} \bar{P}_b^{\text{C}} = \bar{P}_b^{\text{C}} w_{b,k,t}^{\text{Ch}}, \quad (13)$$

1.3 Strong Duality

In order to linearize the bilinear term $\lambda_t^{\text{Th}} H_{b,t}^{\text{Th,B}}$ we utilize strong duality as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{b=1}^B \sum_{t=1}^T (\lambda_t^{\text{Th}} H_{b,t}^{\text{Th,B}} + \lambda_t^{\text{Retail}} P_{b,t}^{\text{El}} \\ & - \lambda_t^{\text{FiT}} P_{b,t}^{\text{PV,FiT}} + u_b \sigma_t \epsilon_{b,t}) \\ & + \lambda^{\text{CfP}} \sum_{b=1}^B P_b^{\text{peak}} = \sum_{b=1}^B \sum_{t=1}^{T-1} \gamma_{b,t}^{\text{dyn}} \left[-(1 - \alpha_b) \right. \\ & \quad \left. (T_t^{\text{Amb}} + R_b H_{b,t}^{\text{Gain}}) \right] \\ & - \sum_{b=1}^B (\gamma_b^{\text{ref},1} + \gamma_b^{\text{ref},T}) T_{\text{in}}^{\text{ref}} + \sum_{b=1}^B \sum_{t=1}^T \gamma_{b,t}^{\text{PV}} P_{b,t}^{\text{PV}} \\ & - \sum_{b=1}^B \sum_{t=1}^T \bar{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{comf}} (T_{b,t}^{\text{des}} + \bar{T}^{\text{comf}}) \\ & + \sum_{b=1}^B \sum_{t=1}^T \underline{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{comf}} (T_{b,t}^{\text{des}} - \underline{T}^{\text{comf}}) \\ & - \sum_{b=1}^B \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{t=1}^T \mu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{Hp}} \theta_{k,t} \bar{P}_b^{\text{Hp}} \\ & - \sum_{b=1}^B \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{t=1}^T \mu_{b,k,t}^{\theta\text{Ch}} \theta_{k,t} \bar{P}_b^{\text{C}} \\ & - \sum_{b=1}^B \sum_{t=1}^T \bar{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{Line}} \bar{P}_b^{\text{Line}} \end{aligned}$$

1.4 Linearization of complementary slackness conditions

In order to linearize these constraints, we apply the same Big-M method to all of them. Since the procedure is identical for each case, we illustrate it using only one representative example.

$$s_{b,t}^{\text{up}} = T_{b,t}^{\text{des}} + \bar{T}^{\text{comf}} + \epsilon_{b,t} - T_{b,t}^{\text{in}}, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (14)$$

$$s_{b,t}^{\text{up}} \geq 0, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (15)$$

$$0 \leq \bar{\mu}_{b,t}^{\text{comf}} \leq M_{b,t}^\mu \delta_{b,t}^{\text{up}}, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (16)$$

$$0 \leq s_{b,t}^{\text{up}} \leq M_{b,t}^s (1 - \delta_{b,t}^{\text{up}}), \quad \forall b, t. \quad (17)$$

$$\delta_{b,t}^{\text{up}} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall b, t. \quad (18)$$

1.5 Input parameters

This section provides all the network or building-related parameters.

$$\text{COP}_{\text{GSHP}}(\Delta T) = 10.29 - 0.2084 \Delta T + 0.001322 \Delta T^2 \quad (19)$$

$$\text{COP}_{\text{WSHP}}(\Delta T) = 9.99 - 0.2049 \Delta T + 0.001249 \Delta T^2 \quad (20)$$

Table 1: Daily ToU schedule

Time window	$\lambda^{\text{El,Ret}}$ (€/kWh)	λ^{FiT} (€/kWh)
00:00–07:00	0.112	0.0144
07:00–11:00	0.211	0.0288
11:00–14:00	0.337	0.0432
14:00–18:00	0.211	0.0288
18:00–22:00	0.337	0.0432
22:00–24:00	0.112	0.0144

Table 2: Per-building thermal & size inputs

b	Type	R (K/kW)	C (kWh/K)	A_{floor} (m ²)	A^{PV} (m ²)
1	Office	5.73	1.89	200	300
2	House 1	0.31	7.17	81	40
3	House 2	0.82	7.76	307	80
4	House 3	1.36	3.56	449	100
5	House 4	1.53	3.53	334	50

Table 3: System Parameters and Inputs

Parameter	Description	Value
\mathcal{T}	Horizon length (h)	96 (4 seasonal days)
B	Number of buildings	5 (1 office, 4 dwellings)
K	Temperature intervals	1
Δt	Time step (h)	1
d^{chg}	Demand charge (€/kW)	3
kA^{netw}	Network heat-loss coeff. (kW/K)	3.7
V^{netw}	Network volume (m ³)	10.3
V^{ACC}	ACC volume (m ³)	20
ρ^{w}	Water density (kg/m ³)	1000
c^{w}	Water heat capacity (kJ/kg·K)	4.186
ΔT^{diff}	Warm-cold separation (K)	8
$S^{\text{ACC_cap}}$	ACC energy capacity (kWh)	190
S_0^{ACC}	ACC initial energy (kWh)	$0.5 S^{\text{ACC_cap}} = 95$
$\underline{T}^{\text{Netw,H}}/\overline{T}^{\text{Netw,H}}$	Warm pipe bounds (°C)	10/22
$\underline{T}^{\text{Netw,C}}/\overline{T}^{\text{Netw,C}}$	Cold pipe bounds (°C)	14/36
$P_{\text{cap}}^{\text{line}}$	Elec. line cap per building (kW)	300
$\overline{P}^{\text{EH,HP}}$	EH heat pump max (kW _{el})	300
$\overline{P}^{\text{EH,Ch}}$	EH chiller max (kW _{el})	300
$\overline{P}_b^{\text{HP}}$	Building HP max (kW _{el})	(150, 45, 45, 45, 45)
$\overline{P}_b^{\text{Ch}}$	Building chiller max (kW _{el})	(150, 45, 45, 45, 45)
A_b^{PV}	PV area per building (m ²)	(300, 40, 80, 100, 50)
η^{PV}	PV efficiency	0.18
$T_{\text{office}}^{\text{des}}/T_{\text{res}}^{\text{des}}$	Desired indoor temp. (°C)	22/22
T^{comf}	Comfort half-band (°C)	1.0
$\underline{T}^{\text{in}}/\overline{T}^{\text{in}}$	Indoor temp. bounds (°C)	15/27
$T_{\text{ref}}^{\text{in}}$	Initial/final indoor anchor (°C)	20
ϵ^{max}	Comfort slack bound (°C)	7
q_{occ}	Gains per person (W/person)	73 + 55 = 128
$q_{\text{light}}/q_{\text{equip}}$	Lighting / equipment (W/m ²)	9/15
d_{occ}	Design density (m ² /person)	10
N_b^{des}	Design occupants (-)	(20, 5, 5, 5, 5)
R	Price box factor (-)	1.5
$\lambda_{\text{ref}}^{\text{H}}/\lambda_{\text{ref}}^{\text{C}}$	Price refs (€/kWh _{th})	$\approx 0.048/0.056$
M_T	Big-M for ΔT (K)	8
M	Big-M	10^3